

Analyzing the behavior of different classification algorithms in diabetes prediction

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ABSTRACT

Diabetes is one of the deadliest diseases in the world that can lead to stroke, blindness, organ failure, and amputation of lower limbs. Researches state that diabetes can be controlled if it is detected at an early stage. Scientists are becoming more interested in classification algorithms in diagnosing diseases. In this study, we have analyzed the performance of five classification algorithms namely naïve Bayes, support vector machine, multi layer perceptron artificial neural network, decision tree, and random forest using diabetes dataset that contains the information of 2000 female patients. Various metrics were applied in evaluating the performance of the classifiers such as precision, area under the curve (AUC), accuracy, receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve, f-measure, and recall. Experimental results show that random forest is better than any other classifier in predicting diabetes with a 90.75% accuracy rate.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Diabetes is a well-known chronic disease that poses a significant issue in the world health systems. The pancreas releases the insulin hormone, which permits glucose to transit from food to the bloodstream [1]. Diabetes is caused by the lack of insulin and can result in serious damage such as coma, heart attack, weight loss, cardiovascular dysfunction, blindness, ulcer, and damage of the nerve system [2]. In 2020, 10% of the United States population has diabetes according to centers of disease control and prevention (CDC) [3]. Studies show that the number of people having diabetes will reach 25% in 2030 [4]. The availability of accurate early prediction can significantly reduce the risk and severity of diabetes.

Over the last few years, there was a growth in the number of applications that use artificial intelligence in diagnosing diseases such as breast cancer [5], [6], Alzheimer [7], parkinson's disease [8], coronary artery disease [9], skin disease [10], anxiety and depression disorders [11]. The use of classification algorithms in computer-aided diagnoses systems has helped in the detection of diseases at an early stage. The main goal of this study is to find which classification algorithm achieves minimum error rate in predicting diabetic patients without human involvement. The early detection of diabetes can enhance the treatment process and save the patient's life.

In this research, we will evaluate the performance of different classification algorithms like an artificial neural network, decision tree, support vector machine, random forest, and naïve Bayes using a diabetes dataset. In recent years, several data mining techniques were used to predict diabetes. The use of such methods has helped in early detection, which resulted in minimizing the complication of diabetes. The summary of literature review is illustrated in Table 1.

Table 1. Summary of literature review

Ref.	Dataset Description	Implemented Method	Accuracy
Paul <i>et al.</i> [12]	consists of 392 instances and 8 features	evaluated the performance of 3 classifiers (random forest, support vector machine, and logistic regression). Random forest attains the highest accuracy	84%
Dey <i>et al.</i> [13]	consists of 768 instances and 8 features	used artificial neural network with min-max scaler	82%
Swapna <i>et al.</i> [14]	consists of Electrocardiograms (ECG) of 20 people	extracted complex features from heart rate variability data using long short-term memory, conventional neural network (CNN) and fed them to support vector machine	95%
Zhu <i>et al.</i> [15]	consists of 768 instances and 8 features	used PCA, k-mean and logistic regression	97%
Wu <i>et al.</i> [16]	consists of 768 instances and 8 features	used k-mean and logistic regression	95%
Tripathi and Kumar [17]	consists of 768 instances and 8 features	implemented different predictive analysis algorithms. Random forest achieved the highest accuracy rate	87%
Li <i>et al.</i> [18]	consists of 768 instances and 8 features	used metaheuristic algorithm with k-mean	91%
Husain and Khan [19]	not specified	implemented an ensemble model by combining the propabilities of different machine learning algorithms.	96%

Paul [12] analyzed the performance of three classification algorithms; random forest, support vector machine, and logistic regression in predicting diabetes. The results show that random forest algorithm achieves a high accuracy rate of 84% than support vector machine and logistic regression. Dey *et al.* [13] implemented a web application for diabetes prediction. The implemented model used an artificial neural network among different classification algorithms like support vector machine, k-nearest neighbor, and naïve Bayes. The proposed model of artificial neural network and min-max scalar achieves a high accuracy rate of 82% compared to other classification algorithms.

Swapna *et al.* [14] implemented a methodology to extract complex features from heart rate variability data using long short-term memory, conventional neural network (CNN). These features are fed into support vector machine for diabetes prediction. The proposed system achieved a 95% accuracy rate.

Zhu *et al.* [15] proposed a data mining framework to diagnose diabetes. The framework used principal component analysis to address the correlation issue in the feature set, a k-mean clustering algorithm to clean the data from outliers, and a logistic regression algorithm to classify the data. The proposed framework was able to successfully classify the data with a 97% accuracy rate.

Wu *et al.* [16] suggested a two-stage framework to diagnose diabetes. In the first stage, the incorrectly clustered data are eliminated using an improved k-mean algorithm; the resulting dataset is then used in the following stage as input to the logistic regression algorithm to classify the data. The model attains a high accuracy rate of 95%.

Tripathi and Kumar [17] used several predictive analysis algorithms namely support vector machine, linear discriminant analysis, random forrest, and k-nearest neighbor. The study shows that Random Forrest algorithm gives a high accuracy rate of 87% compared to other algorithms. Li *et al.* [18] implemented a diabetes prediction model using a k-nearest neighbor algorithm. The proposed system used metaheuristic algorithms with k-mean to select features. The model achieves a good accuracy rate of 91%. Husain and Khan [19] proposed a diabetes prediction model by merging the probabilities of different machine learning algorithms into an ensemble model.

In our research, the performance of different machine learning algorithms in diagnosing diabetes is evaluated. The research aims to find the algorithm that achieves the maximum accuracy in identifying diabetes at an early stage. The remainder of this study is organized as follows; Section 2 discusses the algorithms applied in this study and the structure of the dataset. Section 3 shows the results of different classification algorithms, and this study is concluded in section 4.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

2.1. Data set description

In this paper, we used diabetes dataset that can be found in Ukani [20] to assess the performance of different classification algorithms. The dataset contains medical information of female patients. The dataset consists of 8 numeric features and one target class to determine if a patient has diabetes or not (0 or 1). The diabetic dataset contains the information of 2000 female patients. In data preprocessing, we removed noise and outliers. The dataset is divided into train and test datasets with a test size equal to 20%.

2.2. Model design and implementation

In this paper, we analyzed the behavior of different classification algorithms to predict diabetes. The procedure used in this study is illustrated in Figure 1. Different machine learning algorithms namely artificial neural network, random forest, support vector machine, decision tree, and naïve Bayes have been implemented to find the algorithm that achieves the minimum accuracy rate in predicting diabetes.

Figure 1. Diagram of the proposed model

2.2.1. Artificial neural network

One of the main algorithms in machine learning is an artificial neural network. They are designed to mimic the behavior of the human brain; it consists of input, hidden and output layers. The hidden layer is responsible of finding hidden information in the input data and translates it into a form that the output layer can use [21]. Figure 2 illustrates the architecture of the applied artificial neural network in this study.

Figure 2. The architecture of the artificial neural network

2.2.2. Random forest

Random forest is a well-known classification algorithm that is utilized in solving regression and classification problems. It gets the prediction from multiple decision tree classifiers that work on parts of the dataset instead of the entire dataset. The performance of the model increases, when the number of classifiers increases [22]. We implemented a random forest model using Python libraries.

2.2.3. Support vector machine

Support vector machine is a powerful classification algorithm that is used in regression and classification. Support vector machine works by finding the best hyperplane that separates between different classes of the data. The data are plot in m -dimensional space where m represents the number of features [23]. We implemented support vector machine using Python libraries.

2.2.4. Decision tree

A decision tree is a supervised learning algorithm. It focuses on generating rules from the training data that are used to predict the class. Decision tree consists of a root, branches, and leaf nodes. One of the

most challenging points in decision tree is selecting the feature that best split the data [24]. We implement a decision tree algorithm using Python libraries.

2.2.5. Naïve bayes

It is a probabilistic machine-learning algorithm that depends on Bayes theorem. All features are independent and irrelevant from each other is assumed in naïve Bayes algorithm. One of the main advantages of naïve Bayes is its ability to work with data problems such as imbalanced datasets and missing values [25]. We implement it using Python libraries.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Classification algorithms performance is assessed using a variety of metrics like precision, receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve, recall, F-measure, accuracy, and area under the curve (AUC) [26], [27]. Five classification algorithms were evaluated in our study namely artificial neural network, naïve Bayes, random forest, decision tree, and support vector machine. The result of different classification algorithms in terms of true positive, true negative, false positive, and false negative are illustrated in Table 2.

Table 2. Confusion matrix of different classification algorithms

Model		Actual	
		Non-diabetic	Diabetic
Artificial Neural Network	Non-diabetic	235	28
	Diabetic	58	79
Decision Tree	Non-diabetic	239	24
	Diabetic	72	65
Gaussian NB	Non-diabetic	216	47
	Diabetic	54	83
Random Forrest	Non-diabetic	250	13
	Diabetic	22	115
Support vector machine	Non-diabetic	230	33
	Diabetic	73	64

Table 3 illustrates that random forest performs better than any other classifiers with regard to precision, recall, accuracy, and F-measure. On the other hand, support vector machine obtains the minimum accuracy rate of 73.50%. For more qualitative demonstration, Figure 3 depicts the ROC curve of the classification algorithms. Random forest ROC curve is closest to the top left corner than any other classifiers. We also measure the performance of the classifiers using AUC to show which classifier has high separation ability between different classes. Figure 4 shows that random forest obtains a high AUC value of 0.88.

Table 3. Performance measures for various classification algorithms

Model	Accuracy (%)	F-measure (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)
Artificial Neural Network	78.50	74.64	77.01	73.50
Decision Tree	76.00	70.40	74.94	69.16
Gaussian NB	74.75	71.61	71.92	71.36
Random Forrest	90.75	89.48	90.63	88.59
Support vector machine	73.50	67.99	70.94	67.08

Figure 3. ROC curve for various classification algorithms

Figure 4. AUC scores of various classifiers

4. CONCLUSION

Diabetes is an incurable disease that affects 9% of the world's population. Diabetes can lead to serious complications if it is not probably treated. As a result, diabetes prediction at an early stage is critical in the treatment process. We have analyzed the performance of multiple machine learning models namely artificial neural network, support vector machine, random forest, Gaussian naïve Bayes, and decision tree using diabetes dataset for 2000 female patients. We conclude that random forest surpasses other machine learning models in diagnosing diabetes with a 90.75% accuracy rate and 0.88 AUC score.

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